

OPTIMIZATION OF MILLING / HOMOGENIZATION PROCEDURES AND PRESSING PARAMETERS FOR OBTAINING TRANSPARENT ND-YAG CERAMICS FOR LASER APPLICATION

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1. ABSTRACT

In order to obtain transparent Nd-YAG ceramics from commercial oxide powders, it is necessary to optimize appropriate homogenization procedures and pressing parameters. Commercially available high purity Nd₂O₃ powders often have mean grain size above 10µm and require a preliminary milling step in order to obtain a submicronic granulometry. Pellets of 2at%Nd-YAG were prepared by solid-state reactive sintering. After the homogenization and before pressing, the mixture of Y₂O₃, Nd₂O₃ and Al₂O₃ requires a granulation step. Several granulation procedures were compared. Spray drying parameters were optimized in order to obtain unbroken spherical agglomerates. Unfortunately these parameters caused a variation in the stoichiometric ratio.

2. INTRODUCTION

The preparation of the first translucent YAG samples was obtained in 1984 [1], and in 1995 it was demonstrated that it is possible to obtain a laser effect from doped YAG ceramics obtained by solid-state reactions [2, 3]. The preparation of transparent YAG ceramics of large dimensions nevertheless is still a difficult task. The best way to obtain good reproducible results seems to produce green bodies applying slip-casting. Compared to pressing of granulated powders, slip casting of nearly-newtonian slurries produces more homogeneous green bodies with higher densities [4]. Nevertheless examples of optical transparency obtained by pressing procedures are reported in literature [5]. Since we had already reached satisfying transparency values on small samples by pressing [6], we attempted to optimize pressing and granulation procedures in order to produce larger samples. The main problem was represented by the occasional appearance of macroscopic defects. Ammonium stearate is a well known internal lubricant that could help in avoiding such problems [7] but also PVA plasticizers, such as PEG200 and PEG400, can be used to reduce green defects and increase green density [8, 9].

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

High purity commercial Nd₂O₃ (Cerac) was employed. Since mean grain size was over 10µm, it was preliminary milled for 150 hours in a polyethylene bottle, obtaining a mean grain size of 400-500 nm. High purity 3-4mm alumina balls (GMHDA-4mm, Mattech Corporation,

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Cincinnati, Ohio) were used; alumina introduced by ball milling was evaluated. The resulting powder was titrated and kept under N₂ atmosphere, in order to protect from CO₂. Nd₂O₃ prepared in this way was used together with commercial high purity Al₂O₃ (mean grain size of 300 nm) and Y₂O₃ (mean grain size of 700 nm) to prepare aqueous slurries with the corrected stoichiometric ratio to produce 2 at% Nd-YAG. Dolapix CE64 (Zschimmer and Schwartz) 0.6 wt% was used as a dispersant; 2 wt% PVA 15000 was added as a binder. TEOS 0.5 wt% was used as a sintering aid. The pH was adjusted by adding quantities of citric acid (CA from now on) between 0.15 and 0.6% wt%. Ammonium stearate (0.5wt%) was tested as internal lubricant. The ceramic slurries were ball-milled for 20 hours in a polyethylene bottle before granulation. Granulometry was controlled prior granulation with a Coulter N4S. Viscosity was measured at 20°C with an Haake RV20 rotational viscosimeter. Spray drying was performed in a Buchi 190 Mini Spray dryer. Operating parameters are discussed subsequently. For performing freeze drying, a laboratory vacuum stove was connected to a rotative pump; a liquid nitrogen trap was used to protect the pump from vapours. Liquid nitrogen was used to freeze a ceramic suspension, poured in a stain steel container. Spray-freeze drying was performed by spraying the ceramic suspension into liquid nitrogen. This procedure strongly reduces drying times. The granulated powder was uniaxially pressed into 13.6 mm diameter pellets, and cold isostatically pressed at pressures between 150 and 300 MPa. Dewaxing was performed in flowing air, 2h at 800°C, with an heating ramp of 20°C/h. Sintering of YAG pellets was performed at 1700°C for 15h in alumina crucibles loaded in a high vacuum tungsten furnace. Vacuum values were kept around $1.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ Pa also during heating ramps (5°C/min). In order to avoid “black samples”, colour centres were eliminated with a treatment of 1 h at 1400°C in air or inert gas. SEM observations were performed, using a LEO 438 VP (Cambridge), equipped for EDS microanalysis (Oxford-ISIS 300).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Optimization of rheological properties for homogenizing

It resulted that the addition of an acid is necessary to maintain the pH at the optimal value. If the pH was not corrected, the quantity of water which is necessary to prepare a suspension with the commercial ceramic powders we considered was very high (maximum solid content 0.6g/ml) and the measured pH value resulted 9.2. 80g of ceramic powders required 130g of water. After 20 hours of milling in a 250ml PE bottle, pH reached the value of 9.9. The alumina ball (80g) consumption was around 20 mg. On the contrary, correcting the pH of the freshly prepared suspension between 7 and 8, a solid content of 1.2 g/ml was reached: 80g of ceramic powders were suspended in 68 ml of water and effectively ball milled with 80g of alumina balls in a 250 ml bottle. With 0.6 wt% of CA, we registered an initial pH value of 7.2, but the flow curve (Fig. 1a) evidences high viscosity and strong deviation from newtonian behaviour. Starting with a pH value of 8.0 (Fig. 1b), obtained by adding ammonia (around 0.7ml) to a portion of the previous suspension, lower viscosity and a nearly -newtonian behaviour was obtained.

After 20 hours of milling with the alumina balls, both suspension (initial pH 7.2 and initial 8) increased the pH value, to 9.2 and the flow curves (Fig. 2) were very similar, with a viscosity less than half of the initial value. However the alumina ball consumption was around 80mg, four-times the value obtained with no pH correction and a low solid content.

In order to test higher initial pH values, it was necessary to reduce the percentage of CA. With 0.3% CA, an initial pH value of 8.3 was obtained; with 0.15% CA, an initial pH value of 8.8. Corresponding flow curves are reported (Fig. 1c, 1d). In both cases the measurements of pH and of the flow curve after 20 hours milling were impossible, due to high viscosity.

To correct pH we used a citric acid, as is reported in literature [4]. Other weak acids can be used effectively and even strong acids, if the acid is added to the solution before the powders (in order to avoid the dissolution of Y_2O_3 and Nd_2O_3). In any case, the quantity of acid which is necessary depends on the powders characteristics, so an empirical optimization is needed.

Figure 1. Flow curves the suspensions prepared at different initial pHs. (a) pH=7.2: CA 0.6%; (b) pH=8.0: CA 0.6% and NH_3 (in red); (c) pH=8.3: CA 0.3%; (d) pH=8.8: CA 0.15%.

Figure 2. Flow curve of a suspension prepared with an initial pH 8, after 20 hours of milling.

4.2 Optimization of spray drying parameters

In our previous experience with spray dried powders, even optimizing cold isostatic pressure conditions, small macroscopic defects could not be completely avoided in the transparent sintered samples. Observations on granulated powders evidenced that some of the granules were broken (Fig. 3).

Figures 3 and 4. SEM images of a granulated mixed oxide powder with different parameters.

Figure 3. Aspirator 8; flow 600; inlet T: $195^\circ C$; outlet T: $125^\circ C$; pump: 4.5 ml/min.

Figure 4. Aspirator 13; flow 800; inlet T: $185^\circ C$; outlet T: $130^\circ C$; pump: 4.0 ml/min.

In order to optimize flowability of the powders, we optimized spray drying parameters in order to obtain a more homogeneous granulated powder, with unbroken granules (Fig. 4). The drying air flow and the aspiration rate were significantly increased, while the pump rate was decreased to the minimum value. The new parameters also increased the yield of the process, reducing the quantity of material which remained adherent on the glass parts. Since no possible disadvantages were initially identified, the new parameters were adopted for the following experiments.

4.3 Comparison of granulation techniques through microstructural investigations

SEM operating parameters were optimized in order to show grain size and phase impurities in a single observation. By operating in partial vacuum, with high probe currents (1200pA), low distances (7-9mm), EHT of 20 keV and a BS detector it was possible to clearly identify the grains (without thermal or chemical etching) together with porosity (which appear black, with charging effects) and residual phases, which can be alumina (black, without charging effects) of Y and Nd rich phases (white). Nd-YAG pellets were prepared following the previously reported experimental procedures. A ceramic suspension prepared at pH 8 was divided into several parts in order to compare different granulation techniques. Initially we compared spray drying (with the optimised parameters, Fig. 4) and freeze drying. Fig. 5 and 6 show how pellets obtained from freeze dried powders contain an excess of alumina. The microstructure is inhomogeneous and affected by abnormal grain-growth. The macroscopic consequence of this microstructure is that pellets are not fully transparent. On the other hand, spray dried powders resulted in a completely different homogeneous microstructure (Fig. 7 and 8), with no residual alumina and a residual white phase. The white phase was analysed by EDS and resulted rich in Y_2O_3 and Nd_2O_3 . Initially the different stoichiometric ratio was attributed to sedimentation during freezing. So spray-freeze drying and spray drying were compared, using the same peristaltic pump and the same nebulizer, but the different stoichiometry was confirmed. So it was the spray drying the cause of the alteration of the ratio between the elements, probably because a preferential loss of alumina (the ceramic powder with the minimum mean grain size) induced by the drying air flow.

Figures 5 and 6. SEM micrographs of YAG samples obtained from freeze dried powders.

Figures 7 and 8. SEM micrographs of YAG samples obtained from spray dried powders.

4.4 Optimization of pressing parameters

Since SEM observation had demonstrated that only spray dried powder had the right stoichiometric ratio (just a small excess of Y_2O_3 and Nd_2O_3 , how it can be deduced from Fig. 8), the pressing procedure was optimized only for this powder. In Fig. 9 we report a photo of three pellets, prepared at different CIP pressure. We found these values of green density: 52.5% of the theoretical value at 300 Mpa, 49.5% at 200 MPa, 47.5% at 150 Mpa. As a theoretical value of density we used 4.58g/ml, the value we found for highly transparent samples with this composition.

Transparency of sintered samples certainly represents an easy and effective way of evaluating mean characteristics of YAG samples (much more effective than comparing density values). With high CIP pressure, more macroscopic defects are obtained. Quantitative evaluation of transmittance values confirmed that applying high CIP pressures, pellets with decreased transparency are obtained. So the optimal CIP pressure for spray dried powders is 150Mpa, even if green density is considerably lower. Probably the optimal CIP pressure would be different by using internal lubricant. Previously we had tested the use of ammonium stearate verifying that an increase of the green density of around 1% can be obtained. However in that case the sample was not transparent and the presence of macroscopic defects couldn't be verified.

Figure 9. Sintered YAG samples (11mm height). A, B and C prepared at 150, 200 and 300 Mpa respectively. Macroscopic defects can be seen in samples B and C.

Transmittance values:

A=83.2%; B=76.9%; C=77.8%

YAG doped monocrystal=84.0%

5. CONCLUSIONS

The preparation of a stable slurry of Al_2O_3 , Y_2O_3 , Nd_2O_3 was optimised for the production of transparent 2at% Nd-YAG by pressing: a pH correction was necessary in order to obtain high solid content and low viscosity. The attempt to optimize the spray drying parameters caused an alteration of the stoichiometric ratio, probably because of a preferential loss of alumina with the air flow. So a comparison between freeze drying, spray-freeze drying and spray drying was not possible. The pressing procedure for spray dried powder was optimized and good transmittance (99% of the theoretical value) was obtained with a CIP pressure of 150MPa. The use of an internal lubricant was tested, but further investigations are needed: a small increase in green density was found, but we could not verify the effect on macroscopic defects, because sintered samples were transparent.

SEM observations were optimized in order to evaluate all the significant parameters (residual phases, porosity and grain size) in a single observation. The data reported gives an idea of how strongly the stoichiometric ratio influences the microstructure.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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